

Reactions of Ninhydrin with N-Substituted Anilines and Substituted Guanidine

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Ninhydrin (I) reacts with N-methyl-, N-ethyl- and N-benzyl- aniline to yield, 1,3-indandione derivatives of type II. These products are stable and yield well-crystallised acetyl derivatives. A similar reaction takes place between I and 1,3-diphenylguanidine to yield III. The reaction of I with diphenylamine proceeds differently to give a compound of the structure IV.

THE colour reactions of amino acids with ninhydrin are quite well known and were studied by a number of workers¹⁻¹⁴. Like amino acids, imino acids also give coloured products with ninhydrin and were studied by Grassmann and Arnim^{15,16}, McCaldin¹⁷ and other authors¹⁸⁻²¹. Newberg²² showed

ed that many aliphatic primary amines gave Ruhemann's purple⁵ with ninhydrin. These reactions were further investigated by other workers^{6,7,11,14,23}. The reactions of cyclic secondary amines with ninhydrin were originally studied by Grassmann and Arnim^{15,16} and later reinvestigated by McCaldin¹⁷.

Methylamine was reported as one of the products in reactions of ninhydrin with N-methylamines²⁴. The reactions of ninhydrin with aromatic primary amines were studied by Friedman²⁵, Ruhemann⁵ and Moubasher²⁶. Recently Shapiro^{27,28} found that reactions of ninhydrin with the amino heterocycles guanine and cytosine afforded products that stood in contrast to earlier reports about the reactions of ninhydrin with simpler aromatic amines and ureas. He, therefore, reinvestigated some of the reactions²⁹ and reported the formation of cyclised product with aromatic amines and ureas with ninhydrin. In the present paper we wish to report the reactions of ninhydrin with some N-substituted anilines and 1,3-diphenylguanidine.

N-methyl-, N-ethyl-, and N-benzylaniline reacted with ninhydrin (I) in aqueous medium to give the corresponding 1,3-indandione derivatives (IIa, b and c). The products crystallised well, and gave well defined spots on thin layer chromatography (t.l.c.) The products agreed with those reported earlier as 1 : 1 adducts having the structure of type II. Increase of molar ratio of ninhydrin and N-substituted anilines to 1 : 2 did not yield any 1 : 2 adduct. No methylamine formed during the reactions as reported earlier (*loc. cit.*). N-benzylaniline did not undergo the reaction till refluxed.

The reaction of 1,3-diphenylguanidine with ninhydrin in 0.1N H₂SO₄ yielded a white crystalline product to which was assigned the structure III on the basis of its elemental analysis, infrared spectrum and formation of acetyl and 2,4-DNP derivatives. It reacted like the N-substituted anilines but the reaction in water was slow in absence of acid.

The increase in reaction rate in 0.1N H₂SO₄ may be attributed to the increase in positive character of carbonyl carbon of ninhydrin in acid medium.

On the other hand, diphenylamine reacted with ninhydrin in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 in aqueous medium to yield a compound to which the structure IV was assigned on the basis of its elemental analysis, ultraviolet and infrared spectra and 2,4-DNP. The rate of the reaction increased by a factor of about two when it was carried out in 0.1N H₂SO₄. No reaction took place in alcohol medium. Quantitative estimation of the 2,4-DNP showed the presence of three carbonyl groups in IV. The fact that all the carbonyl groups did not form 2,4-DNP was evident in the infrared spectrum of the 2,4-DNP which showed an absorption band at 1700 cm⁻¹. This is probably due to the steric hindrance. Probable mechanism of formation of IV is shown here :

Operation of the electronic shift shown by curved arrows results in ready elimination of H₂O in V, which is expected to be enhanced by an acid. The fact that the reaction doubles in 0.1N H₂SO₄ lends support to the proposed course. A similar mechanism was also envisaged by Johnson and McCaldin¹⁴ in the reactions of ninhydrin with cyclic α -aminoacids

Experimental

As ninhydrin, N-substituted anilines, guanidine, diphenylamine and the reaction products gave well

defined spots, the progress of the reactions was followed by t.l.c. on silica gel plates. Solvents used

were benzene-ethyl acetate (50 : 50) for N-methyl-, and N-ethylaniline; benzene-methanol (95 : 5) for N-benzylaniline and diphenylamine; methanol in the case of 1,3-diphenylguanidine and spots detected with iodine vapour. The infrared spectra were run in nujol mull and the intensities of bands are expressed as s (strong), m (medium), w (weak) and sh (shoulder).

Reaction of Ninhydrin with N-Methylaniline. Formation of (IIa) :

Ninhydrin (3.56 g., 0.02 mole) in water (75 ml) was added to N-methylaniline (2.14 g., 0.02 mole) in water (50 ml). The mixture was stirred at 30° for 18 hr. The fluffy yellow product was separated, dried under vacuum and crystallized twice from hot ethanol yielding IIa as needles, m.p. 163°-164°; yield 3.74 g. (66%). (Found : C, 72.19, H, 4.91; N, 5.16. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 71.90; H, 4.91; N, 5.24%).

The infrared spectrum of the compound showed absorptions at 3315(m), 2800(sh), 1715(m), 1685(s), 1592(s), 1500(m), 1365(s), 1280(sh) cm^{-1} .

The acetyl derivative crystallized from acetic acid-water, m.p. 258°-260°; IR bands at 2800(sh), 1735(m), 1705(m), 1613(w), 1575(w), 1360(broad), 1285(w), 1240(m) cm^{-1} .

The 2,4-DNP crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 224°-225° (decomp.). Quantitative estimation revealed presence of two carbonyl groups. [Found : CO, 20.09. $C_{16}H_{13}O_3N$ requires CO (for two), 20.93%].

Reaction of Ninhydrin with N-Ethylaniline. Formation of (IIb) :

The preparation was analogous to that conducted with N-methylaniline. An orange coloured product (IIb) was obtained. It was crystallized twice from hot ethylacetate as needles, m.p. 204°-205°; yield 2.48 g (83%). (Found : C, 72.31; H, 5.24; N, 4.81. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 72.60; H, 5.34; N, 4.98%).

The infrared spectrum of the product showed absorptions at 3360(m), 1740(m), 1705(s), 1602(s), 1520(m), 1370(s), 1330(m), 1260(m) cm^{-1} .

The acetyl derivative crystallized from acetic acid-water, m.p. 162°-164°; IR bands at 1740(sh), 1710(m), 1630(w), 1500(m), 1350(broad), 1285(m), 1240(broad) cm^{-1} .

The 2,4-DNP crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 218°-220° (decomp.). Quantitative estimation showed the presence of two carbonyl groups. [Found : CO, 19.35. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N$ requires CO (for two), 19.91%].

Reaction of Ninhydrin with N-Benzylaniline. Formation of (IIc) :

The preparation was analogous to that conducted with N-methylaniline. In this case no reaction was observed at 30°. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 17 hr. A yellowish grey coloured solid (IIc) that formed was crystallized twice from hot ethanol, m.p. 200°-202°, yield 2.55 g. (77%). (Found : C, 76.68; H, 4.81; N, 4.02. $C_{22}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 76.96; H, 4.95; N, 4.08%).

The infrared spectrum of the compound showed absorptions at 3325(w), 1745(w), 1695(s), 1600(m), 1502(w), 1370(s), 1280(w) cm^{-1} .

The acetyl derivative crystallized from acetic acid-water as white needles, m.p. 97°-98°; IR bands at 1740(sh); 1690(m), 1630(w), 1600(m), 1570(s), 1365(s), 1285(w), 1250(w) cm^{-1} .

The 2,4-DNP crystallized from hot ethanol, m.p. 164°-165° (decomp.). Quantitative estimation revealed the presence of two carbonyl groups. [Found : CO, 15.75. $C_{22}H_{17}O_3N$ requires CO (for two), 16.33%].

Reaction of Ninhydrin with 1,3-Diphenylguanidine. Formation of (III) :

A mixture of ninhydrin (0.89 g., 0.005 mole), 1,3-diphenylguanidine (1.056 g., 0.005 mole) and 0.1N H_2SO_4 (80 ml) was stirred for 17 hr. at 30°. The white solid (III) that formed was filtered, dried and crystallized twice from methanol-chloroform, m.p. 211°-213° (decomp.). (Found : C, 70.93; H, 4.49; N, 11.23. $C_{22}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires C, 71.16; H, 4.58; N, 11.32%).

The infrared spectrum of the product showed absorptions at 3330(broad), 1705(s), 1640(s), 1565(broad), 1520(m), 1365(s) cm^{-1} .

The acetyl derivative crystallized from acetic acid-water, m.p. 124°-126°; IR bands at 1750(sh), 1720(s), 1680(m), 1670(m), 1605(m) cm^{-1} .

The 2,4-DNP crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 216°-219°.

The reaction of ninhydrin and 1,3-diphenylguanidine was complete after 2 hr when it was conducted at 70° and the same product III was obtained.

Reaction of Ninhydrin with Diphenylamine. Formation of (IV) :

A solution of ninhydrin (3.56 g., 0.02 mole) in water (75 ml) was added slowly to a stirred solution of diphenylamine (3.38 g., 0.02 mole) in water (50 ml). After stirring for 20 hr no reaction was observed at 30° and 60°. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 21 hr. T.l.c. showed that all the ninhydrin reacted but some diphenylamine was left unreacted. The resulting greenish yellow solid mixed with a gummy material was filtered and the residue washed several times with ether whereby the gummy material went into ether solution. The solid (IV) was crystallized twice from hot ethanol, m.p. 253°-254°, yield 2.80 g. (40%). (Found : C, 76.08; H, 3.47; N, 2.84. $C_{30}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 76.43; H, 3.64; N, 2.98%).

The infrared spectrum of the compound showed absorptions at 1690(m), 1670(m), 1590(m), 1365(s) cm^{-1} . The ultraviolet spectrum of this compound showed λ_{max}^{EtOH} at 347, 314, 251, and 228 nm.

The 2,4-DNP crystallized from hot ethanol, m.p. 158°-159° (decomp.); IR bands at 1700(s), 1670(sh), 1590(m), 1570(m), 1560(s), 1520(m) cm^{-1} . Quantitative estimation showed the presence of three carbonyl groups. [Found : CO, 17.59. $C_{30}H_{17}O_3N$ requires CO (for three), 17.82%].

Another reaction of ninhydrin (0.89 g., 0.005 mole) with diphenylamine (0.845 g., 0.005 mole) was carried out in 0.1N H₂SO₄ (80 ml) in similar manner as described above. The reaction was complete after 11 hr on refluxing and the same product IV was obtained.

In another experiment ninhydrin (1.78 g., 0.01 mole) in water (75 ml) was added to diphenylamine (0.845 g., 0.005 mole) in water (50 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 21 hr when all the ninhydrin and diphenylamine were consumed as shown by t.l.c. and the same product IV was obtained.

Another reaction of ninhydrin with diphenylamine was conducted in analogous manner to that described above except that alcohol was used as solvent. No reaction was observed after 25 hr of refluxing.

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